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TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN ENGLISH

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Teaching Mathematics in English to students of other Languages

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TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN ENGLISH

Abstract

When the language of education is English, teaching mathematics to foreign language students raises some important issues. Teaching mathematics requires a variety of linguistic skills that foreign students may not have dominated. The strategies described in this paper will provide effective practices for incorporating teaching mathematics for foreign students.

Keywords: Math skills, Language role, Misconception, Dilemmas, Second language

TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN ENGLISH

Teaching Mathematics in English to students of other Languages

The human being often starts learning a language in the womb. As a matter of course this language is called mother tongue and it becomes person's native language. However, learning a foreign or a second language generally starts in kindergarten age, i.e. 4-5 years after birth. That is why adults who learned second language later than this age mostly do not feel comfortable when they speak a language other than their mother tongue.

Beside languages, students in the world begin studying mathematics at around five or six years old, continuing through secondary school and into higher education. In elementary school, children are introduced to basic mathematics. And the theories and methods covered in math classes become increasingly complex at that age. During elementary school, students are taught basic arithmetic: addition, subtraction, multiplication and division. These concepts are elaborated on in secondary school where students will study basic algebra and concepts of variable, integers and polynomials.

The language which is used to convey mathematical ideas to students has become a topic of increased concern to mathematics educators in recent years. Educators claim that students who do not understand English are effectively foreclosed from any meaningful education.

Mathematics educators working with students, whose native language is not English, need to be more informed of what is known about the complex process of learning a second language. Some of the academic languages used in materials and discussions in the mathematics classes may be especially difficult for second language learners to follow. Another critical consideration is the age at which the second language is learned.

Language and Mathematics Learning

Perhaps more than any other subject, teaching and learning mathematics depends on language. The acquisition of mathematical ability is a subtle process, but dialogue between the learner and teacher is imperative, and this depends on effective communication.

Mathematics is about relationships: relationships among numbers, categories, geometric forms, variables and so on. In general, these relationships are abstract in nature and can only be brought into being through language. Even mathematical symbols must be interpreted linguistically. Thus, while mathematics is often seen as language free, in many ways learning mathematics fundamentally depends on language. Learners' mother tongue can play an important role in their learning of mathematics. Some educators suggest that students need a high degree of proficiency in at least one language in order to make satisfactory progress about math skills at school. They also propose that students with strength in two or more languages will do better their peers, while those without a high degree of proficiency in any language will underachieve.

The interest in the relationship between language and learning is not new. Some theorists have suggested that language determines and defines thoughts. Others have tended to accept only a limited effect of

TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN ENGLISH

language on thought, stressing the role of earlier conceptual learning in language development and the shifting meanings of words as concepts continue to develop. Although researchers have long recognized the vital role that language plays in mathematics performance, but they have not always acknowledged its equally important role in the process of getting mathematical skills and concepts.

Challenges Encountered

Finding a balance between focusing on mathematics and focusing on language is perhaps the biggest challenge of teaching mathematics to learners whose second language is English. Some educators highlighted several dilemmas that arose for teachers in their multilingual mathematics classrooms. One of these dilemmas “clarity” concerned the visibility of, or explicitness of attention to, mathematical language. This issue was raised by one of the teachers participating in the study, who reflected on an event where a female student gave an explanation to the rest of the class: Here, there is a tension between the teaching of correct language and the students’ understanding of mathematics. To what extent, is correct mathematical English necessary to do mathematics? This event also illustrates a second dilemma “intervene or not to intervene”. By intervening, the teacher may shift students’ attention from the mathematics they are grappling with to the language used to explain mathematics. Intervening may allow the student to give an explanation using more mathematical language, but the resulting explanation might not be the explanation she has given for herself. On the other hand, intervention might disempower her student. Also, offering a language for students can empower them to develop their thinking.

We believe that the culture of the classroom let students make mathematics meaningful for themselves by interacting with both the teacher and other students. Our observations let us conclude that the “legend” that mathematics transcends language is detrimental to the interests of English second language students. Furthermore, students need opportunities to discuss problems in order to understand them. This is not to suggest that teachers must design problems based on the lives of their students. It is difficult for any teacher to be familiar with students’ different cultures, languages and backgrounds. However, activities can be designed to allow learners to bring their experiences and interests to mathematics.

Mathematics can be particularly challenging to students of other languages because mathematical knowledge consists of three components: linguistic knowledge, conceptual knowledge, and procedural knowledge.

1.Linguistic Knowledge: Mathematics is not limited to performing computations in isolation; it is dependent on the English language role. Academic standards in mathematics require students to apply computational skills in a variety of real-life problem-solving situations, read and solve word problems, communicate their mathematical thinking, and collaborate with their peers to complete a task.

Mathematics has its own specialized language, grammatical patterns, and rules. While students of other languages are learning English, they must also learn the unique meanings that some English words have in a mathematical context. Here are some linguistic challenges that students of other languages may encounter in classroom lectures, discussions, and textbooks.

In order to understand mathematics, students must:

TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN ENGLISH

- a. learn many content-specific vocabulary words (i.e., quotient, equivalent, divisor).
- b. know the meaning of many complex phrases (i.e., least common multiple, greatest common factor).
- c. understand that many common English words have unique meanings in mathematics (i.e., bring down, tree, face, plane, cone, net, positive, negative).
- d. understand that prepositions (i.e., by, with, to, into, from, etc.) are used in a variety of ways in word problems to signal operations.
- e. know the meaning of prefixes and suffixes (i.e., hept-, tri-, bi-, poly-, -gon, -lateral).
- f. understand unique mathematical sentence constructions (i.e., If $x=3$, then calculate x^2+2x+2).
- g. understand statements and questions that are written in passive voice (i.e., twenty is divided by five)
- h. know that mathematical operations are associated with many different words.

2. Conceptual Knowledge: Mathematics requires a conceptual understanding of a mathematical process in order to choose the correct operation(s) and perform the necessary steps to derive an answer. Some mathematical concepts can be very concrete, while others are abstract. To help students of other languages succeed in the mathematics classroom, teachers need to connect previous knowledge and experience to new concepts that are being taught.

A student of other languages may have learned the mathematical concept in a native language but may not have the English language development to understand a discussion, read a textbook, or be able to express his or her understanding. In this case, the student of other languages does not need to re-learn the concept but must learn new English words to talk about a previously learned concept. If the mathematical concept is new to the student of other languages, then the teacher must make the instruction more concrete, visual, collaborative, and hands-on.

3. Procedural Knowledge: Just as one mathematics textbook differs from another textbook in its approach to teaching a concept, various cultures around the world approach computation using different methods. This can cause great disappointment and often confusion for students of other languages. Here are some procedural challenges that students of other languages may encounter in classroom lectures, discussions, and textbooks:

- a. Students of other languages may be accustomed to reading and writing from right to left instead of from left to right. The teacher needs to explicitly teach the student of other languages the expected procedures for using a notebook and completing homework problems.
- b. Students of other languages may have learned a different way to write letters and numerals (0-10). The teacher needs to show student of other languages the expected method to write letters and numerals to avoid misconceptions when reading homework or answers on tests.
- c. Periods are used instead of commas in some cultures to separate multiples of a thousand (i.e., 1,5 could be written as 1.5).
- d. Most students of other languages are familiar with the metric system, and writing amounts of money (i.e. \$15 could be written as 15\$) but have never studied the other system.
- e. Some students of other languages learn to add, subtract, multiply, and divide using different computational methods.

TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN ENGLISH

Without a clear understanding of how mathematics in classrooms can be culturally different and challenging for students of other languages, teachers may make false assumptions. Teachers of students of other languages can assist the students by:

- a. being aware of cultural differences so they can understand academic behaviors and performance in the mathematics class.
- b. clearly teaching students of other languages the class expectations about writing in notebooks, completing homework assignments, and solving computations using the procedure taught in class.

Implications for Teaching

Teaching mathematics in English to students of other languages is complex. These students bring with them a wide range of languages, proficiencies, experiences and expectations. While, in the light of this complexity, specific methods are unlikely to be universally applicable, some broad principles can be suggested as starting points for reflection: be aware of the specific linguistic demands of mathematics and, where appropriate, highlight and discuss aspects of mathematical English with your students; find out about English second language students' mother tongue, their levels of proficiency, and their math skills in other languages; and promote English second language students' mathematical meaning-making through problem solving, problem posing, and opportunities for discussion.

Word problems are often challenging for students. In tests, they generally get them wrong. However, when given the opportunity to explore how word problems work, most of the students find them straightforward; they are able to develop explicit understanding of an aspect of mathematical English, as well as of the relationship between words and mathematics.

They succeeded, in part, through making them their own. There is not necessarily a correct response to the dilemmas mentioned above. However, one general approach does emerge from research findings. If children are to learn mathematics, there needs to be a focus on mathematical meaning-making.

TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN ENGLISH

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